

Organisational Support as a Basis for Technology Management of Library Staff in University Libraries in Lagos and Ogun States Nigeria

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Abstract

Background: Technology Management (TM) study how technology is developed, acquired, and positively used with a focus on how science and basic knowledge are combined to create useful goods for an institution. However, evidences established low extent of technology management by staff in university libraries lacking in knowledge and strategic of handling different units of technological resources in the library on area of value in Lagos and Ogun States, Nigeria. Organizational support (OS) is seen as a basis for the operation of TM.

Methodology: Survey research design was adopted for the study. The study population comprised 364 library staff in 22 public and private universities. The researchers used total enumeration to collect data from the respondents using structure and validated questionnaire. Four larker style table was used and Cronbach alpha coefficient constructs ranged from 0.70 to 0.95. Respondents' rate was 299 (90.1%) Data analysis was conducted using descriptive and inferential (simple regression) statistics. at a 5% significance level

Findings/Results: Organizational support had positive and significant influence on technology management ($\text{Adj } R^2 = 0.35$, $F(2, 295) = 0.449$, $p < 0.05$) of library staff in university libraries in Lagos and Ogun States Nigeria. Social network support $\beta 211$ $t(3.074) = .0.000$ $p < 0.05$, and tangible support $\beta 283$ $t(4.139) = .0.000$ $p < 0.05$) had positive influence on technology management of library staff in Lagos and Ogun State, Nigeria.

Implications: The implication is that library staff should accept and utilize a high level of technology management.

Conclusion: The study concluded that organizational support is an essential basis that can contribute to technology management of library staff in Lagos and Ogun States, Nigeria.

Recommendations: The study recommended that the management of universities Library should prioritize resource allocation to support technology infrastructure and staff development

Keywords: Organisational support, Technology management, Library staff and University libraries

Introduction

Management is key to every library establishment. Therefore, it is the process of formally getting things done in an organization through the leadership of a manager, overseeing the work done in an institution. Technology management encompasses a collection of ideas, skills, methods, and procedures that facilitate decision-making and execution related to the creation and application of technology by organizations, with the ultimate goal of fostering innovation and enhancing organizational competitiveness. Through technological advancements, technology management creates and adapts to changes in the environment. Institutions can rapidly advance in performance technologies, adapt to shifting environmental conditions, and meet the continually rising competitive demands of technology management. This implies that the only way for sustainability to thrive and development to occur in an institution of learning, especially in libraries, is through effective technology management. According to Ersin and Cetindamar (2015), technology management is a process of managing technological assets as a prerequisite for staff developing decision-making skills to improve technology management in technology-intensive organizations. Technology management is the study of how technology is developed, acquired, and positively utilized, focusing on combining science and basic knowledge to create valuable assets for an organization or institution

Technology management concerns a number of tasks, such as: identifying and assessing potentially valuable technologies, choosing and implementing strategies to gain access to necessary technologies, identifying and utilizing new technologies, establishing the best organizational structure for managing new technologies, creating protocols for safeguarding and upholding intellectual property rights related to new technologies and setting up scanning and forecasting processes to foresee future trends in technology development and use. According to Gutterman (2023); Yamamoto and Pujotomo (2006), there are five general activities that comprise technology management, including: identifying technologies, choosing technologies that will assist the organization, procuring and integrating specific technologies, utilizing technologies to yield advantages Safeguarding knowledge and skills integrated into goods and production processes

Technology management is significant in that it provides a strategic view of handling different units in the library, enabling librarians to manage technological resources effectively. This creates an understanding of the precise actions the institution takes to carry out its strategic performance plan. Strategic management is the process by which organizations adapt to external and internal changes and trends in globalization. According to Root (2014), strategic management involves the formulation of organizational goals characterized by several fundamental ideas. Technology management informs the library's strategic position by making informed choices for future management actions. The library's success depends on the availability of technical tools for librarians' use and their ability to effectively utilize Information Communication and Technology (ICT) to improve job performance. Like other institutions, libraries must ensure compatibility with the ever-changing operating environment to survive

Technology management can be underpinned by indicators such as technology process, technology acquisition, technology absorption, technology innovation, and technology transfer. However, technology process in university libraries faces obstacles including: limited technical skills among staff, such as: inability to start up and shut down computers and other devices. Difficulty to navigating computer systems and devices. lack of knowledge in searching for information within computer systems. Technology requisition challenges, including: inability to make requisitions for standardized computer systems. difficulty signing into high-standard computer systems or devices. inability to employ qualified repairers or recommend suitable computer system purchases. Furthermore, library staff struggle with technology absorption, including: lack of carefulness when operating computer systems. failure to monitor computer systems for errors or issues. inability to identify and explain errors in the computer system to coworkers. These challenges hinder the effective development, assimilation, and utilization of technological knowledge and capabilities in libraries

Innovation support is a crucial indicator for measuring technology management in university libraries. Unfortunately, library staff struggle with transforming new ideas or methods into functional tools or software. According to Coccia (2021), innovation support is a vital component of the technological system, aiming to meet adopters' demands, accomplish objectives, and resolve issues. However, library staff tend to rely on traditional methods of service instead of embracing modern technological operations. They are expected to support the development of new technology, but this is hindered by their limited adoption of innovative approaches. Technology transfer is another key indicator of technology management in university libraries. As defined by Swamidass and Vulasa (2009), technology transfer involves moving research work and information sources from one entity to another for further development and commercialization. Library staff face challenges in this area, including: Inability to

transfer information between computer systems and devices. limited ability to use collaborative methods for sharing information. Difficulty transmitting information to users through computer systems. Inability to share links with users via computer systems. These challenges highlight the need for improved technology management and innovation support in university libraries

As a matter of fact, organizational support is the foundation for improving technology management. Organizational support can positively influence the challenges faced with technology management. Organizational support refers to the idea that employees perceive their organization as respectful and caring towards them. According to Sun (2019), organizational support reflects the value placed on employees' contributions and their well-being. It involves providing favorable relationships with employees, encouraging them to work diligently. Organizational support is about employees' perceptions of how much their organization values their contributions and cares about their well-being. Organizational support encompasses two key aspects: valuing employees' contributions and prioritizing employees' well-being and interests. When employees feel valued and supported, they are more likely to have a positive connection with the organization, leading to improved outcomes.

Organizational support can be measured using indicators such as social network support and tangible support. These two predictors stand out as effective ways to improve technology management in university libraries. Social network support enhances a person's sense of communication and connection within a particular group of people sharing similar interests or circumstances. This involves interactions between staff members in an institution, where they associate with one another to solve complex issues. According to Campbell and Wright (2002); Pires (2018), social network support encompasses a range of behaviors, including empathy, confrontation, compassionate participation, caring, encouragement, and dependable friendship bonds. On the other hand, tangible support, as an indicator of organizational support, provides beneficiaries with necessary products and services in a concrete manner. This includes giving out money, material things, or services. Tangible support facilitates the gathering, handling, storage, and accessibility of data and information resources for library users. This encompasses various sources, including: information media, hardware, software, equipment, protocols and standards, personnel, technologies. While several studies have explored the variables of this study in combination with other variables and in different contexts, none have been conducted combining these variables in the specific study locale. Therefore, this study aims to investigate the influence of organizational support as a basis for technology management of library staff in university libraries in Lagos and Ogun States, Nigeria."

Statement of the Problems

Technology management involves the study of how technology is developed, acquired, and utilized, with a focus on combining science and basic knowledge to create valuable assets for organizations or institutions. According to Gregory (1995): Yamamoto and Pujotomo (2006), technology management encompasses activities such as: identifying technologies, choosing technologies that support organizational goals, procuring and integrating specific technologies, utilizing technologies to yield advantages, safeguarding knowledge and skills integrated into goods and production processes. However, librarians in university libraries face challenges due to limited knowledge of technology management and strategic handling of technological resources. They struggle with: technology process, technology acquisition, technology absorption, technology transfer, technology innovation.

Organizational support has been recognized as a foundation for enhancing staff knowledge, skills, and abilities to efficiently use technology management. According to Sun (2019), organizational support reflects the value placed on employees' contributions and their well-being. It is a perception by employees that their organization values their work and cares about their welfare. Although several studies have explored organizational support in various contexts, none have combined the variables of this study in the specific study locale. Therefore, this study aims to investigate the influence of organizational support on technology management among library staff in university libraries in Lagos and Ogun States, Nigeria."

Objective of the study

The main objective of this study is to investigate the influence of Organizational Support as a basis for Technology Management of library staff in university libraries in Lagos and Ogun States, Nigeria. However, the specific objectives of the study are to:

1. ascertain the extent of technology management of library staff in university libraries in Lagos and Ogun States, Nigeria
2. determine the level of organizational support of library staff in university libraries in Lagos and Ogun States, Nigeria
3. ascertain the influence of organizational support on technology management of library staff in university libraries in Lagos and Ogun States, Nigeria and
4. ascertain the relative influence of organizational support (components) on technology management of library staff in university libraries in Lagos and Ogun States, Nigeria.

Research Questions

Based on the above-mentioned specific objectives the following are the research questions formulated to provide answers to the study. They are:

1. What is the extent of technology management of library staff in university libraries in Lagos and Ogun States, Nigeria
2. What is the level of organizational support of library staff in university libraries in Lagos and Ogun States, Nigeria

Research Hypotheses

The null hypothesis is formulated and will be tested at 0.05 level of significant

1. Organizational support has no significant influence on technology management of library staff in university libraries in Lagos and Ogun States, Nigeria
2. Organisational support (components) have no significant influence on technology management of library staff in university libraries in Lagos and Ogun States, Nigeria

Literature review

Concept of Technology Management

Technology management is a collection of ideas, aptitudes, methods, and procedures that lead to decision-making and execution concerning the creation and application of technology by organizations, with the ultimate goal of fostering innovation and boosting competitiveness (Ersin & Cetindamar, 2015). According to Gutterman (2023), technology management encompasses five general activities: identifying technologies, choosing technologies that support organizational goals, procuring and integrating specific technologies, utilizing technologies to yield advantages safeguarding knowledge and skills integrated into goods and production processes. Libraries, as organizations, ensure the availability of IT resources, including hardware, software, networking, and data, as well as IT support for their employees (Mukhtar & Maidabino, 2021). Organizational leaders should prioritize IT strategy for successful hybrid work and technology management.

Concept of Organizational Support

Organizational support refers to the resources, structures, and systems provided to employees to help them perform their jobs effectively and reach their full potential. This support includes: training programs, mentorship opportunities, access to technology and tools flexible work arrangements, health and wellness initiatives and positive work culture. In libraries, organizational support involves resources, systems, and structures

that help librarians excel in their roles and meet the information needs of their patrons effectively. This support can be seen in various ways, including: professional development, access to resources, work environment, well-being initiatives, recognition and reward systems, leadership and governance and community engagement support. A supportive organizational atmosphere can create an environment that relieves employees' mental stress (Islam & Ahmed, 2019) and encourages them to contribute to the organization's success (Adegbaye, 2020). Employees' perceptions of organizational support can come from three sources: management, supervisors, and coworkers (Prasetio et al., 2020).

Theory. The Technology Acceptance Model (TAM), introduced by Davis is one of the most widely used models to explain user acceptance behavior. Grounded in social psychology theory, particularly the Theory of Reasoned Action (TRA), this model elucidates how users form attitudes and intentions to use technology (Heijden 2000). Organizational support can be integrated into TAM as a factor influencing perceived usefulness and ease of use of technology.

Implications:

Understanding the role of organizational support in technology acceptance informs strategies to promote technology adoption among library staff.

Library administrators can utilize this knowledge to design and implement effective support systems, enhancing technology management and utilization.

The study's findings contribute to extending TAM, highlighting organizational support's significance in shaping library staff's technology acceptance behaviors

Methodology

A descriptive survey research design was adopted for this study. Descriptive research design involves observing all variables and subjects at one point in time without attempting to manipulate or control the subjects. According to Ojo (2003), descriptive design provides access to people's attitudes or opinions towards situations, events, organizations, or procedures, using questionnaires, interviews, or direct observation to collect data. The total population for this study was 364 library staff from 22 universities in Lagos and Ogun States, Nigeria, comprising 2 federal universities, 3 state universities, and 17 private universities. Since the population was manageable, a total enumeration technique was used, and questionnaires were administered to all 364-library staff. Out of these, 299 questionnaires were returned. To ensure the reliability of the instrument, a Cronbach Alpha reliability test was conducted. The test measures the internal consistency or reliability of a set of survey items. The results

showed that the 20 items on technology management had a Cronbach Alpha value of 0.938, while the 14 items on organizational support had a value of 0.926, indicating that the instrument was highly reliable for data collection. Data analysis was performed using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 23. The SPSS was used to analyze coded data responses, generating descriptive and inferential statistics. Descriptive statistics, such as frequency count, percentage, mean, and standard deviation, were used to answer research questions. Hypotheses were tested using regression analysis, including single linear regression and multiple regression

Result analyses

Table 4.1 Technology management of library staff in university libraries Lagos and Ogun States, Nigeria

Technology management Indicate your extent of technology management in	Very High extent (4)	High extent (3)	Low extent (2)	Very Low extent (1)	Mean	Std
Technology process					3.53	0.46
My ability to start up a computer and other devices in the office is to a	179 (60.1%)	114 (38.2%)	05 (1.7%)	0	3.56	0.53
My ability to navigate through all areas of a computer and other devices in the place of work is to a	169 (56.7%)	121 (38.2%)	08 (2.7%)	0	3.54	0.55
My knowledge of searching an information in the computer system and other devices is to a	159 (53.5%)	147 (42.8%)	11 (3.7%)	0	3.50	0.57
My ability to short down computer system and other devices in the work place after using it is to a	162(54.5%)	119 (40.1%)	16 (5.4%)	0	3.49	0.60
Technology acquisition					3.41	0.51
Requisition for a standardise computer system or device for library use is to a	141 (47.2%)	148 (49.5%)	10 (3.3%)	0	3.44	0.56

The request to operate a high standard computer system in the library is to a	137 (46.9%)	148 (49.5%)	11 (3.8%)	0	3.43	0.57
The idea to employ an assistant of qualify repairers for any challenges encounter with the system is to a	142 (47.5)	143 (47.8)	14 (4.7%)	0	3.43	0.58
My recommendation for purchase of good computer system or other devices in the library is to	138(46.2%)	142 (47.5%)	19 (6.4%)	0	3.40	0.61
Ability to reach on to use neighbouring institutions equipment for the benefits of users is to a	131 (44.0%)	145 (48.7%)	22 (7.4%)	0	3.37	0.62
Technology absorption					3.40	0.56
Ability to dictate errors while working with the system or other devices when something went wrong is to a	144 (48.5%)	136 (45.8%)	17 (5.7%)	0	3.43	0.60
Ability to explain to a co-worker the state whereby a system or other devices position itself is to a	140 (47.5%)	136 (46.8%)	19 (6.4%)	0	3.41	0.61
My attention to check computer system while working is to a	142 (47.7%)	130 (43.6%)	26 (8.7%)	0	3.39	0.64
Technology innovation					3.36	0.54
Process of transforming new ideas or methods of operation into functional tools and software to users is to	146 (49.3%)	127 (42.9%)	23 (7.8%)	0	3.42	0.53
The ability to support development of new technology is to	143(48.3%)	131 (44.3%)	22 (7.4%)	0	3.41	0.63
The ability to support modern operation of	131 (44.1%)	146 (49.2%)	20 (6.7%)	0	3.37	0.61

technology in the library is to						
Technology transfer					3.36	0.48
My ability to send and move information from one computer system to another devices is to a	135 (45.9%)	149 (50.7%)	10 (3.4%)	0	3.43	0.54
My ability to use collaborative method to share information from one computer system to another devices is to a	139 (47.4%)	133 (45.4%)	21 (7.4%)	0	3.40	0.62
My ability to transmit information on computer system for useability of user in the library is to a	127 (43.1%)	148 (50.2%)	20 (6.8%)	0	3.36	0.64
My ability to share link to other computer system or other devices is to a	123 (42.0%)	152 (51.9%)	18 (6.1%)	0	3.36	0.60
My ability to accept link from other computers system is to a	125 (43.9%)	130 (45.6%)	30 (10.5%)	0	3.33	0.66
Technology management (Average Weighted Mean =3.42)						

Source Researchers Field Survey, 2024

The result above showed that the extent of technology management of library staff in university libraries in Lagos and Ogun States, Nigeria was high (\bar{x} = 3.42) on a scale of 4. Technology management was measure by five indicators: (Technology process, technology acquisition, technology absorption technology innovation, and technology transfer) Further details depict that technology process (\bar{x} =3.53) which was at very high extent while other indicators as technology acquisition (\bar{x} =3.41), technology absorption (\bar{x} = 3.40) technology innovation (\bar{x} = 3.30), and technology transfer (\bar{x} =3.36) showed high extent.

Table 4.2 Organizational support of library staff in university libraries in Lagos and Ogun States, Nigeria

Organizational support Kindly indicate your level of support....	Very high level (4)	high level (3)	High level (3)	Very low level (2)	Low level (1)	Mean	Std
Social network support						2.99	0.76
The rate at which my organization is willing to help us take decision is to	102(34.1%)	118(39.5%)	118(39.5%)	71(23.7%)	08(2.7%)	3.05	0.83
Counting on my organization when things go wrong is to	95(31.8%)	122(40.8%)	122(40.8%)	72(24.1%)	10(3.3%)	3.01	0.83
Compassionate participation in my organization is to a	89(29.8%)	130(43.5%)	130(43.5%)	71(23.7%)	09(3.0%)	3.00	0.81
Interaction with other to solve user problem is to a	90(30.1%)	120(40.1%)	120(40.1%)	77(25.8%)	12(4.0%)	2.96	0.85
Giving good attention to listen to users' problem is to	88(29.4%)	116(38.8%)	116(38.8%)	81(27.1%)	14(4.7%)	2.93	0.87
Tangible support						2.87	0.87
Providing necessary product and service is to	98(33.0%)	135(45.5%)	135(45.5%)	61(20.5%)	03(1.0%)	3.40	0.75
Getting financial assistant from the institution is to	74(24.7%)	125(41.8%)	125(41.8%)	86(28.8%)	14(4.7%)	2.87	0.84
Gathering and making data	81(27.1%)	128(42.8%)	128(42.8%)	80(26.8%)	10(3.3%)	2.83	0.82

available to individual is to							
The information media is to a	75(25.2%)	126(42.3%)	77(25.8%)	20(6.7%)	2.86	0.88	
Having good hardware in the institution is to a	74(24.8%)	112(37.6%)	83(31.3%)	19(6.4%)	2.81	0.88	
Having good software in the institution is to a	77(25.9%)	105(35.4%)	94(41.6%)	21(7.2%)	2.80	0.91	
Providing good protocol by personnel of our institution is to a	65(22.2%)	124(42.3%)	83(28.3%)	21(7.2%)	2.80	0.87	
The provision of standard equipment by the institution is to	73(24.6%)	109(42.3%)	88(29.6%)	27(9.1%)	2.77	0.92	
Organizational support (Average Weighted Mean =2.90)							

Source Researchers Field Survey, 2024

The result above showed the extent of organizational support of library staff in university libraries in Lagos and Ogun States, Nigeria was high (\bar{x} = 2.90). The table further revealed that social network support was rated at (\bar{x} =2.99) while tangible support was rated at (\bar{x} =2.87). This showed that the two indicators were at high level.

Table 4.3 Simple linear Regression Analysis of Organizational support and Technology management of library staff in university libraries

Predictors	<i>B</i>	<i>Bata</i> (<i>B</i>)	<i>2022/2023</i>	<i>P</i>	<i>R</i> ²	<i>Adj</i> <i>R</i> ²	<i>F</i>	<i>ANOV</i> <i>A (Sig)</i>
(Constant)	2.645		28.756	0.000				
Organizational support	0.2.645	0449	8.671	0.000	0.202	0.199	75.188	0.000

Dependent Variable Technology Management
 Predictor Constant Organizational support
 DF F Statistic = 1.297
 DF F Statistic=296

Source: Field Survey Results, 2024

The above result showed that organizational support had a significant and positive influence on technology management (*Adj R*² = 0.35, *F* (2, 295) = 0449 *p* < 0.05) of library staff in university libraries in Lagos and Ogun States, Nigeria This implied that organizational support to library staff predict technology management in university libraries in Lagos and Ogun States, Nigeria in the study area. Hence the null hypothesis which stated that technology management of library staff in university libraries in Lagos and Ogun States, Nigeria had no significant influence technology was rejected

Table 4.4 Multiple Regression Analysis of Relative Influence of Organizational support (Components) on Technology Management

Predictors	<i>B</i>	<i>Bata</i> (<i>β</i>)	<i>T</i>	<i>P</i>	<i>R</i> ²	<i>Adj</i> <i>R</i> ²	<i>F</i>	<i>ANOV</i> <i>A (Sig)</i>
(Constant)	2.645		28.535	.000				
Social network support	118	211	3.074	.002	0.203	0.197	17.589	0.000
Tangible support	145	283	4.139	.000				

Dependent Variable Technology Management
 Predictor Constant Organizational support
 DF (F Statistic) = 2.297
 DF (F Statistic) =296

Source: Field Survey Results, 2024

The result above showed that the multiple regression analysis for relative influence of organizational support (components) on technology management of library staff in university libraries. According to the result, social network support $\beta 211 t(3.074) = .0.000 p < 0.05$, and tangible support $\beta 283 t(4.139) = .0.000 p < 0.05$ had positive and significant influence on technology management of library staff in Lagos and Ogun State, Nigeria. The components of organizational support (social network support and tangible support) were regressed against technology management using multiple regression analysis.

Summary of Findings

1. The finding revealed that the extent of technology management of library staff in university libraries in Lagos and Ogun States, Nigeria was high
2. The levels of organizational support provided to library staff in university libraries Lagos and Ogun States, Nigeria was high.
3. The result of hypothesis testing revealed that organizational support had a significant and positive influence on technology management in university libraries in Lagos and Ogun States, Nigeria
4. The result of hypothesis testing revealed that organizational support (components) had positive relative influence on technology management in university libraries in Lagos and Ogun States, Nigeria

Implications. The implication is that library staff should accept and utilize a high level of technology management, demonstrating their capability to adapt to new technologies, and ongoing training and support are necessary to sustain this proficiency

Conclusion. This study explores the influence of organizational support on technology management in university libraries. Technology management is crucial for libraries to adapt to changing environments and meet competitive demands. However, library staff face challenges, including limited technical skills, technology requisition issues, and struggles with technology absorption, innovation support, and technology transfer. Organizational support, encompassing social network support and tangible support, is proposed as a foundation for improving technology management. The study aims to investigate the relationship between organizational support and technology management in university libraries in Lagos and Ogun States, Nigeria, highlighting the need for effective technology management and innovation support to enhance library services

Recommendations:

The researcher's recommendations are suggested for the policy intervention:

1. The study recommended that the management of universities Library should prioritize resource allocation to support technology infrastructure and staff development.
2. Library administrators should recognize the importance of organizational support in enhancing technology management.
3. Regular training and workshops should be provided to library staff to enhance their technology management skills as it relates to social network support and tangible support

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